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The Metadata 2020 initiative is an ongoing effort to bring various scholarly communications stakeholder groups together to promote principles and standards of practice to improve the quality of metadata. To understand the perspectives and practices of the main stakeholder groups (librarians, publishers, researchers and repository managers) regarding metadata, the Metadata 2020 Researcher Communications Project Group conducted a survey in the summer of 2019. The survey content was generated by representatives from the stakeholder groups who are active in this Metadata 2020 project.

This document provides a summary of the survey responses, and serves as a companion to the following resources:

- **ANALYSIS PAPER:** Kaiser, K, Urberg, M, Johnsson, M, Kemp, J, Meadows, A, Paglione, L, An International, Multi-Stakeholder Survey about Metadata Awareness, knowledge, and Use in Scholarly Communications. (202X) Location: *To be provided once published*
- **SURVEY QUESTIONS:** Metadata 2020. (2019). Metadata 2020: Survey Questions [PDF]. Location: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4666193>
- **SURVEY RAW DATA:** Metadata 2020. (2019). Metadata 2020 Survey (ALL DATA - Final Survey Export) [Excel spreadsheet]. Location: *To be provided once published*

Demographics

Overall

The survey was released for public participation on June 5, 2019 and closed Monday, July 15, 2019. Participants were notified via direct emails of personal contacts, social media (Twitter, Facebook), blogs, listservs, and online newsletters (Referrer). A total of 222 submitted responses were received from 23 countries. Responses were evaluated for completeness, and any (n=11) that were mostly blank responses were not further analyzed. The analyzed set in total was 211 respondents. Sixty four respondents provided their names and contact information for follow up questions as needed (to clarify free responses). No respondents were contacted for clarification.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 1 Count of Participants by Stakeholder Group and Country

Country	Stakeholder group				Grand Total	% Total
	Librarian	Publisher	Repository Mgr.	Researcher		
United States	48	14	22	10	94	45%
United Kingdom	18	6	12	9	45	21%
Canada	6	1	1	5	13	6%
Australia	3	1	7	2	13	6%
Germany	2	2	4	3	11	5%
Sweden	6			3	9	4%
Netherlands	1	1	1	2	5	2%
France			1	2	3	1%
Italy				2	2	1%
India		1		1	2	1%
Venezuela				1	1	<1%
Switzerland				1	1	<1%
Serbia				1	1	<1%
Saudi Arabia				1	1	<1%
Portugal				1	1	<1%
Norway	1				1	<1%
Nigeria				1	1	<1%
Malaysia				1	1	<1%
Ghana	1				1	<1%
Croatia				1	1	<1%
Brazil		1			1	<1%
Botswana				1	1	<1%
Austria	1				1	<1%
Anonymous				1	1	<1%
Grand Total	87	27	48	49	211	100%

Complete responses among the four stakeholder groups: librarians, researchers, repository managers and publishers. Since the question sets were specific to the target stakeholder group, each group's data is summarized separately. Where possible and with care to avoid risk of losing meaning, free responses were coded into categories to aid in identification of themes or classes of responses. N.B. - Numbers in each response set may not add up to the group total when a response may have covered more than one category, or some items were not selected.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: DEMOGRAPHICS

Table 2 Count and Percentage of Respondents by Stakeholder Group

Stakeholder group	# Respondents	% Total
Librarian	87	41%
Publisher	27	13%
Repository Manager	48	23%
Researcher	49	23%
Grand Total	211	100%

Different survey links were created to better understand how respondents learned about the survey. These link types are described in Tables 3-6 as the “referrer”. Blog links were used on the Metadata 2020 and other blogs. Email links were used when inviting participation via an email or newsletter. Social referral links were used on twitter. Survey links presented in any other setting are listed as having a “Default” referral. Tables 3-6 present responses by stakeholder group, country and referral type.

Librarians (n=87)

Table 3 Percentage of Librarian Respondents by Referral Link Type and Country

% responses	Referrer				TOTAL
	Blog	Other	Email	Social	
United States	11%	11%	32%		55%
United Kingdom	2%	7%	11%		21%
Sweden			7%		7%
Canada	1%	3%	2%		7%
Australia	1%	1%	1%		3%
Germany			2%		2%
Norway				1%	1%
Netherlands	1%				1%
Ghana		1%			1%
Austria	1%				1%
Grand Total	18%	24%	56%	1%	100%

Publishers (n=27)

Table 4 Percentage of Publisher Respondents by Referral Link Type and Country

% responses	Referrer				TOTAL	
	Country	Blog	Default	Email		Social
United States	4%	44%			4%	52%
United Kingdom	11%	4%	4%		4%	22%
Germany	7%					7%
Netherlands	4%					4%
India					4%	4%
Canada	4%					4%
Brazil		4%				4%
Australia					4%	4%
Grand Total	30%	52%	4%	15%	100%	

Repository Managers (n=48)

Table 5 Percentage of Repository Manager Respondents by Referral Link Type and Country

% responses	Referrer				TOTAL	
	Country	Blog	Default	Email		Social
United States	17%	6%	21%		2%	46%
United Kingdom		6%	19%			25%
Australia		15%				15%
Germany		2%	2%		4%	8%
Netherlands			2%			2%
France			2%			2%
Canada			2%			2%
Grand Total	17%	29%	48%	6%	100%	

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: DEMOGRAPHICS

Researchers (n=49)

Table 6 Percentage of Researcher Respondents by Referral Link Type and Country

% responses	Referrer				
Country	Blog	Default	Email	Social	TOTAL
United States	4%	6%	6%	4%	20%
United Kingdom		4%	14%		18%
Canada	2%	4%	4%		10%
Sweden			6%		6%
Germany	4%			2%	6%
Netherlands			4%		4%
Italy			2%	2%	4%
France	2%		2%		4%
Australia		2%		2%	4%
Venezuela			2%		2%
Switzerland	2%				2%
Serbia			2%		2%
Saudi Arabia				2%	2%
Portugal			2%		2%
Nigeria			2%		2%
Malaysia	2%				2%
India			2%		2%
Croatia				2%	2%
Botswana	2%				2%
Anonymous	2%				2%
Grand Total	20%	16%	49%	14%	100%

Librarians (n=87)

Tell us about you

2. What is your library/ information science specialty or subject area?

This question asked respondents to describe their specialty in free text. These responses were grouped into 4 common roles for library services, with a fifth category of miscellaneous 'other' roles.

1. Cataloging, metadata
2. Scholarly communication, publishing, teaching
3. Other areas
4. Research data management, archives management
5. Digital library services

Figure 1 Library/ Information Science Specialty or Subject Area (Librarian, Q2)

Library/ information science speciality or subject area

Summarized and grouped answers

5: digital library services

6.0%

4: research data management, archi...

14.3%

3: other areas

20.2%

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

3. Does your instruction/consultation work include teaching research management software?

Figure 2 Count and Percentage of Librarian Respondents Teaching about Research Management Software (Librarian, Q3)

Tell us about those you work with

The answers in this section reflect how librarians generally work today, and how the profession as librarian has developed during the last years. The profession is highly characterized as being someone who *guides, recommends, instructs* users in different contexts of information research and research publishing.

4. How does your library support metadata education for patrons/ researchers

Respondents were asked to describe in free text how their libraries provide support in metadata education. There was a variety of responses, and responses were grouped into broad categories of support (n=87 responses, complex answers may be counted in more than one category). Some general insights:

- Education is needed on topics including: Online Public Access Catalogs (OPACs), institutional repositories, research data publishing, and information research in general
- Consultations provide opportunities for informally developing metadata education and support services
- Support regarding institutional repositories, such as Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), are often related to the quality of the metadata input in the systems.
- Responses reveal strong correlation between description of metadata support methods to the role indicated by the librarian (Q2). (e.g., catalogers and metadata librarians focus on creating bibliographic records for their catalog, meanwhile reference librarians tend to focus on instruction, consults, and library guides)

These interactions and initiatives were classified into the following categories:

1. Group: Classes and workshops
2. Personalized or Individual: Individual services and consulting
3. Self-Serve: Web-based user guides and software tools
4. Enhancements to Research Assets
5. No answer / Don't know

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

Figure 3 Methods of Metadata Support for Patrons/Researchers (Librarian, Q4)

Methods of metadata support for patrons/researchers

Summarized and grouped answers

The responses break down into the following types of library-researcher interactions or other initiatives to improve researcher outcomes and how they correspond to the summarized and grouped answers:

1:1 Services/Consults	Personalized or individual
Short Library Workshops/Instructions	Group
Documentation/Lib Guides	Self-serve
Library-provided tools/software	Self-serve
In-class instruction	Group
Long Seminar Length Workshops/Instruction	Group
Library Staff-based learning, initiatives, study about metadata	Enhancements to Research Assets
Metadata Enhancements	Enhancements to Research Assets

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

5. What is the role of services for and support of metadata in your library?

Respondents were asked to describe this answer in free text. There was a variety of responses, and responses were grouped into broad categories of support (n=72 responses, complex answers may be counted in more than one category). Some general insights:

- Quality: Metadata quality of library catalogues, discovery systems, CRIS systems etc.; The importance of having *standardized* metadata in systems
- Contribution: Guiding and teaching users in the input of metadata into different systems and in information research.
- Use: Teaching users in metadata is crucial when it comes to teaching in information seeking/research
- Metadata support and services is regarded as a *core function* of many libraries
- 11 respondents didn't understand the question
- 7 respondents provide little or no metadata support to researchers

Select excerpts from write in comments [sic]. The role of metadata services:

- "to enable users to deposit and find research items"
- "Metadata enables access to the Library's collections, so management of the Library's metadata is a core function"
- "Assisting and educating researchers in publishing their research"
- "we are here to help want "FAIR" principles to be followed"

The responses were classified into the following categories:

1. Create/analyze cataloging metadata
2. Support researchers with metadata production
3. Create institutional repository metadata
4. Assist with discovery of research
5. Confused by the question
6. None/limited

Figure 4 Role of Services for, and Support of Metadata (Librarian, Q5)

Role of services for and support of metadata

Summarized and grouped answers

6. How do you interact with the needs of patrons/researchers in your daily work? (select all that apply)

Note: Shortened versions of the text from the survey is presented in the chart below.¹

Figure 5 Methods of Interaction with Patrons/Researchers (Librarian, Q6)

Methods of interaction with patrons/ researchers

% Respondents selecting the choice. Multiple answers encouraged.

Some respondents indicated that they have infrequent direct interactions with patrons/researchers. Two respondents indicated that they didn't understand the question. Other write-in answers included by respondents included

- Scholarly communications topics (Copyright, open access, licensing, publishing, etc.)
- Data management topics (Data curation, management, planning, DOI assignment, etc.)
- Metadata topics (Metadata quality, standards policies, guidance for new material types, etc.)

7. When do patrons most often contact you in the research lifecycle? (select all that apply):

The responses to these questions reflect the types of services that libraries have developed for researchers, such as information searches, publishing support etc. The period between the planning and publishing in a researcher's project is generally quite busy and focused on pure research work, without any direct need for support from the library. Those selecting "other" fell into two groups - those that generally don't work with patrons during the research lifecycle, and those

¹ Text presented to respondents within the survey for question 6 of the librarian survey

1. Writing or providing instructions for research guides (e.g., LibGuides)
2. Individual Research Consultations (e.g., the goal of this consultation is how to conduct research in a given field or for a specific type of project)
3. Item-level cataloging
4. Data deposit consultations
5. Collection level cataloging
6. Group Research Instruction (e.g., the goal of this instruction is how to conduct research in a given field or for a specific type of project)
7. Group Tool-based Instruction (e.g., the goal of this instruction is how to use Tableau or R or other software)
8. Web-based instruction
9. Individual Tool-based teaching sessions e.g., the goal of this session is how to use Tableau or R or other software)

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

providing more specifics of the type of assistance provided (data management plans, data curation, archiving, etc.) Note: Shortened versions of the text from the survey is presented in the chart below.²

Figure 6 Library Contact During Research Lifecycle Stages (Librarian, Q7)

Library contact during research lifecycle stages

% Respondents selecting the stage. Multiple answers encouraged

8. When instructing or consulting with a patron/researcher what types of resources do you typically recommend? (select all that apply):

The three most recommended resources are similar in that they include metadata in a clear and visible manner. Moreover, there is a long tradition among librarians to teach users in information research with the help of abstracting and indexing databases.

² Text presented to respondents within the survey for question 7 of the librarian survey:

- Planning stage: brainstorming, pre-project research ideas, tools for data collection, discussion of analysis at project end
- Post-project publication help
- Mid-project to get help in finding better resources
- Mid-project to get help using tools
- Post-project metadata clean up
- Mid-project for publication submission help

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

Figure 7 Resources Recommended when Consulting with Patrons (Librarian, Q8)

Resources recommended when consulting with patrons

% Respondents selecting the resource. Multiple answers encouraged.

How do you interact with metadata

9. What common questions do you receive from patrons/researchers about metadata?

Respondents were asked to provide an answer in free text. Many respondents, 32 out of 86, either left the question unanswered (15), or answered that they do not work with patrons or otherwise receive questions about metadata (17). In addition, many of the remaining 54 respondents indicated that patrons/researchers do not specifically ask about metadata, but instead ask questions that are related to metadata topics. (Complex answers may be counted in more than one category.)

The responses were classified into the following categories:

1. Create: How to create metadata
2. Search: How to use metadata for search
3. Findability: How to make my items findable
4. What/Why: What is metadata? Why is it important?
5. Enhance: How to enhance or fix metadata

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

Figure 8 Common Types of Questions About Metadata (Librarian, Q9)

Common types of questions about metadata

% respondents that receive questions about metadata. Multiple answers encouraged.

10. If a patron/researcher approaches you about a specific research object in your collection, what are the most critical things you need to know about it before you can help the patron/researcher decide how to use it for their project? (select all that apply)

In this question, the options concerning the practical aspects of finding and using a research object that were selected the most by the respondents. This may be due to the fact that librarians generally are very focused on delivering prompt service and support to the user.

Figure 9 Information Needed to Advise on Resource Use (Librarian, Q10)

Information needed to advise on resource use

% Respondents selecting the choice. Multiple answers encouraged.

Metadata specifics

11. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of metadata for your patrons when they ask for help with a search? (select all that apply)

In this question the respondents listed the types of metadata they feel are most important for search. The fields most often selected as important coincide with those needed in order to find, identify a specific resource to a user. 29 fields were presented for possible selection by respondents³. Fields selected by 25% or more of the respondents are listed below (multiple selection was encouraged)

Figure 10 Most Important Metadata Fields for Search (Librarian, Q11)

Most important metadata fields for search

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

12. What pieces of information do you typically discuss in the context of consultation or instruction with *younger or less experienced researchers*? (select all that apply)

Twenty-nine fields were presented for possible selection by respondents⁴. Fields selected by 25% or more of the respondents are listed below (multiple selection was encouraged)

³ Please see the companion document of survey questions to see the full list of choices.

⁴ Please see the companion document of survey questions to see the full list of choices.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

Figure 11 Fields Discussed When Consulting LESS Experienced Researchers (Librarian, Q12)

Fields discussed when consulting LESS experienced researchers

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

13. What pieces of information do you typically discuss in the context of consultation or instruction with more advanced or expert researchers? (select all that apply)

The results of Q12 and Q13 are similar, there is no major difference in the types of fields that librarians are discussing with young researchers in comparison to what they discuss with more experienced researchers. Although, generally a larger number of fields are discussed with more experienced researchers. 29 fields were presented for possible selection by respondents⁵. Fields selected by 25% or more of the respondents are listed below (multiple selection was encouraged)

⁵ Please see the companion document of survey questions to see the full list of choices.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

Figure 12 Fields Discussed when Consulting MORE Experienced Researchers (Librarian, Q13)

Fields discussed when consulting MORE experienced researchers

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

14. When you talk to patrons/researchers about metadata, what types of standards or schema do you explain or teach? (select all that apply)

Although 41% of respondents indicated that they explain or teach Dublin Core, the same percentage indicated that they teach none of the above or wrote in answers that indicate that they do not teach specific schemas to patrons, but instead teach/ discuss more general concepts. 23% of respondents selected “MARC 21”, a metadata standard very specific to libraries and usually used for the transfer and exchange of metadata between library catalogues; the authors found it surprising for this standard to be taught to patrons. Fewer than 25% of respondents selected any of the other 15 schema/ standards listed⁶.

⁶ Please see the companion document of survey questions to see the full list of choices.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: LIBRARIANS

Figure 13 Standards or Schema Explained/Taught to Patrons (Librarian, Q14)

Standards or schema explained/taught to patrons

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

Publishers (n=27)

Tell us about you

2. What is your job title or professional role

This question asked respondents to describe their job title or role in free text. These responses were grouped into 6 common categories.

Figure 14 Publishing Job Title or Professional Role (Publishing Q2)

Publishing job title or professional role

Summarized and grouped answers

Tell us about those you work with

3. How does your publishing company currently support metadata education for your end users? (Free text)

Respondents were asked to describe in free text how their company supports metadata education. There was a variety of responses, and responses were grouped into broad categories of support n=26 responses, complex answers may be counted in more than one category). The responses were classified into the following categories:

1. None: Do not provide education support
2. Little: Provide little support
3. eResources: Provide self-serve electronic resources
4. Live resources: Provide courses, help desk or other live resources
5. Other: Resources are provided, though the delivery mode is unspecified

Figure 15 Methods of Metadata Education Support for End Users (Publishing Q3)

Methods of metadata education support for end users

Summarized and grouped answers

4. What would you like to see changed in how your company handles education for end users with respect to the metadata they enter and the metadata that is created in the processes of publication? (Free text)

Respondents were asked to describe in free text how their company supports metadata education. There was a variety of responses, and responses were grouped into broad categories of support n=26 responses, complex answers may be counted in more than one category). The responses were classified into the following categories:

Figure 16 Desired Changes in Education Support (Publishing Q4)

Desired changes in education support

Summarized and grouped answers

5. To the best of your knowledge, how is data entered into your system? We enter data in these ways: (select all that apply)

The responses indicate that publishers favor methods that they can directly control for metadata entry. An exception is metadata provided by authors. Note: Shortened versions of the text from the survey is presented in the chart below.⁷

Figure 17 Methods of Interaction with Patrons/Researchers (Publishing Q5)

Methods of interaction with patrons/ researchers

% Respondents selecting the method. Multiple answers encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

- Through our MS submission system--Editorial Manager
- Manually to markup XML file and checked and then automatically
- Automatically by production vendors converting raw content in Word files to structured XML
- The entry point is usually authors via MS submission. Add'l metadata are added during the production process.
- The author and/or I choose BISAC headings, and I put them into the book-supply chain.

⁷ Text presented to respondents within the survey for question 5 of the publisher survey:

- Manually by content experts who work within your organization
- Manually by the researchers depositing the content
- Automatically by internally used software
- Automatically by workflows facilitated by external organizations like ORCID or Crossref
- Manually by content experts who work outside of your organization
- Other - Write in

6. What are the most critical issues for those who submit metadata to your publications? (select all that apply)

The responses suggest that the biggest challenges for metadata submitters are in understanding the impact and benefit that metadata provides. Note: Shortened versions of the text from the survey is presented in the chart below.⁸

Figure 18 Critical Issues for Metadata Submitters (Publishing Q6)

Critical issues for metadata submitters

% Respondents selecting the issue. Multiple answers encouraged

Write in comments [sic]:

- Lack of knowledge about how THEY will benefit from providing information
- Importance of data quality and consistency, i.e., institution names, use of abbreviations
- importance of standards and how that will improve dissemination and discovery, save resources, time and money. Make everything easier internally and externally.
- Lack of controls of data element valid contents; (b) limited multilingualism capabilities by international systems
- Because we publish a variety of content, it can be hard to streamline the submission process to ensure consistency in what and how we are capturing article metadata.

⁸ Text presented to respondents within the survey for question 6 of the publisher survey:

- Lack of knowledge about the impact the metadata will have in discovery
- Lack of knowledge about how end users will benefit from this metadata
- Lack of understanding how your organization uses their information
- Lack of knowledge of specific types of "metadata"
- Lack of understanding how the information they submit is transformed in your system
- Lack of basic knowledge of the term "metadata"
- Time needed to add required information into data fields
- Problems gathering all the needed information for each data field
- Frustrations with manual data entry for different types of research objects
- Other - Write In

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: PUBLISHERS

7. What control do authors/researchers have over the metadata associated with their publications after they have submitted them? (n=26)

Figure 19 Author/Researcher Control Over Metadata (Publisher Q7)

Author/ researcher control over metadata

Author control over metadata associated with their publication after submission

Write in comments [sic]:

- Can request updates via the data team
- not sure
- They can update the majority of their metadata at author proofing stage
- Alert us to make manual changes

How do you interact with metadata

8. Where does your metadata go when it is exported to other systems? (select all that apply)

Write in comments [sic]:

- amazon, apple
- Indexing services, knowledge base vendors, MARC records services
- Google, WoS, Scopus, ScienceOpen, ...
- PMC, JISC Publication Router, Go OA, Scopus, WoS, CNKI, GitHub, Internal APIs, all CC BY or CC0 so we have less knowledge of how else it is harvested
- Search Engines (via crawl)

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: PUBLISHERS

Figure 20 Metadata destination When Exported (Publisher Q8)

Metadata destination when exported

% respondents that selected location. Multiple answers encouraged.

9. Where are the critical issues in your workflows with respect to metadata required for inclusion in your publications? (select up to 5)

Write in comments [sic]:

- None
- Not sure I understand the question

Figure 21 Source of Critical Metadata Issues in Workflow (Publisher Q9)

Source of critical metadata issues in workflow

% Respondents selecting the issue. Multiple answers encouraged.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: PUBLISHERS

10. What are your methods to check the quality of the metadata in your system? (select all that apply)

Write in comments [sic]:

- we ask authors to use MESH terms - usually they don't. We suggest terms and have updated and changed terms but this doesn't always go back to the authors as we've done some of this retrospectively in the process of applying to be indexed

Figure 22 Method to Check Metadata Quality (Publisher Q10)

Method to check metadata quality

% Respondents selecting the choice. Multiple answers encouraged.

Metadata specifics

11. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of metadata in indexing services? (select all that apply)

Figure 23 Most Important Metadata Fields for Indexing Services (Publisher Q11)

Most important metadata fields for indexing services

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

12. What pieces of metadata does your system require for internal publishing tools? (select all that apply)

Figure 24 Required Metadata Fields for Internal Publishing Tools (Publisher Q12)

Required metadata fields for internal publishing tools

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

13. What pieces of metadata does your system require for your online publishing platform? (select all that apply)

Figure 25 Required Metadata Fields for Online Publishing Platform (Publisher Q13)

Required metadata fields for online publishing platform

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.)

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: PUBLISHERS

14. Which standardized metadata schema do you use to describe your published items when you publish them or post them online? (select all that apply)

Figure 26 Metadata Schema Used When Publishing Items Online (Publisher Q14)

Metadata schema used when publishing items online

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

Repository Managers (n=48)

Tell us about you

Combining job title (Q2), collections managed (Q4) and responses about the communities served (Q3), the sectors represented include

Figure 27 Sector Represented (Repository Q2, Q3, Q4)

Sector represented

Derived from job title, collections managed & communities served

2. What is your job title or professional role in your organization?

This analysis represents types of positions, based on self-identified job titles. It shows the variety of positions that work on repositories and the many different types of support it takes to keep repositories functioning and used. It does not, however, reflect how many of these roles are embedded in a library or industry or governmental context. The responses were classified into the following roles:

1. **Librarian:** including Cataloging and Metadata, Data Services, Digital Collections, Research Data and Scholarly Communications, Senior Research Publications and Data
2. **Manager:** including Collections Development, Data Stewardship, Library Research Systems, Open Access, Publications System, Repository, Scholarly Communications
3. **Director or Head:** including, 4TU.Research Data and Digital Repositories Unit, Central Data Management Group, Managing
4. **Specialized:** including Repository, Research Data, or Research Information Manager/Specialist Roles
5. **Archivist:** including Archives Specialist or Archivist Roles
6. **Team Lead Roles:** including Scholarly Communications, Library Research Services, Technical
7. **Other:** including Program Manager Roles (Technical), Associate Director Roles, Coordinator Roles (Digital Initiatives, Research Repository), Data Analyst or Curator Roles, Content Director, Digital Assets Curator, Digital Collections Officer, Group Leader Resource PI (FAIRsharing), IT head of team, Professor, Programmer, Research Data Management Advisor

Figure 28 Repository Manager Job Title or Professional Role (Repository Q2)

Repository Manager job title or professional role

Summarized and grouped answers

3. What research areas does your repository serve?

All respondents answered this question, and more than half (54% | n=26) identified that they collect outputs from all the research areas worked on in their institutions. However, the remaining respondents (46%, n=22) did identify specific topics as the foci of their repositories and most answers included multiple collection areas.

Figure 29 Research Areas Served (Repository Q3)

Research areas served

% indicating the area of the n=22 who specified any area(s). Multiple areas provided by some respondents

4. What types of research objects does your repository store?

75% of respondents included a write-in answer, sometimes in addition to the choices provided. These write in answers were cataloged and grouped to be included in the chart below. These grouped answers are preceded by the word "other"

in the chart below. "Supporting Resources" include maps, events, filed station equipment, survey questions, and measurements.

Figure 30 Research Objects Stored by the Repository (Repository Q4)

Research objects stored by the repository

% indicating the object. Write-in answers grouped & preceded by "Other". Multiple responses encouraged.

Tell us about those you work with

5. What are some common questions you receive from researchers about your repository? (n=42)

This question allowed for free-text entry by respondents. The responses were classified into the following categories:

Figure 31 Common Questions About the Repository from Researchers (Repository Q5)

Common questions about the repository from researchers

Summarized and grouped answers. Some answers fit into more than one question type

6. How well is your organization serving the intended communities, and what are pressing challenges to be addressed? (n=41)

This question had two parts. Only half of those who responded (n=21) answered how well their organization is serving the intended communities.

Table 7 How Well is Your Organization Serving Communities? (Repository Q6)

How well serving communities	# responding	% of those responding
Well/do our best/adequate	17	81%
Unsure/It Depends	3	14%
Poorly	1	5%

In response to the pressing challenges to be addressed, responses generally identified at least one challenge, but most respondents identified more than one. The most frequently reported challenges were with software and other technological infrastructure, followed closely by matters associated with interoperability or integration with other systems and the burdens placed on users (usually academics, scientists or other researchers depositing content).

1. Infrastructure: Internal Software or Data Infrastructure and Technical Challenges (including preserving and storing content and scalability)
2. Interoperability: Integration and Interoperability Challenges Across Repositories (content and metadata)

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: REPOSITORY MANAGERS

3. User Challenges: User Burdens and Hesitancy to Deposit (those depositing content)
4. Metadata Creation: Metadata Creation (access points, controlled vocab, batch work)
5. Content Collection: Content Ingestion and Collection Challenges (including discovery)
6. Staffing Burdens
7. Funding
8. Outreach: Outreach and communications
9. Compliance: Collection Compliance Issues (e.g., 508 compliance)

Figure 32 Pressing Challenges in Serving Intended Communities (Repositories Q6)

Pressing challenges in serving intended communities

% Respondent answers fitting summarized challenge. Multiple answers encouraged.

7. To the best of your knowledge, how is data entered into your system? We enter data in these ways (n=48): (select all that apply)

Figure 33 Methods of Data Entry into Repository Systems (Repository Q7)

Methods of data entry into repository systems

% Respondents selecting the method. Multiple answers encouraged.

Comments were included by many to provide clarification and additional insights [sic]:

- We use multiple methods. Some loaded in batch, some via manual deposit (phasing out), some via a vendor CRIS (Elements), and, soon, some via direct deposits by publishers.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: REPOSITORY MANAGERS

- As products of researcher analytical workflows.
- Manually by faculty liaison/research librarians
- We use Symplectic Elements to harvest metadata
- we do a mix of the above, as our internal curation team also harvest information manually or using schema.org (where this is used by the resource we need to register and list)
- Automatically by workflows facilitated by external research organizations
- Researcher tagging
- manually by archivist
- Theses: manually; other research via Symplectic Elements
- ETDs are automatically loaded and then reviewed by staff.
- Look-up from external organizations
- manually means that I select a file and use the upload feature of our repo, data means primary data, apart from that - metadata is entered by hand in a online form
- Librarians cataloging the document
- What do you mean by 'data' - sorry, I don't understand the scope of the question
- via an integration with a CRIS; through a batch ingest process; through harvesting of ETDs and metadata from our preservation repository, which receives it from ProQuest.
- Combination of Manual and Automatic
- Theses are manually added by Repository staff. All other records are in XML format are added via an ftp server.

8. What are the most critical issues for those who submit metadata to your repository? (select all that apply) (n=48)

Most respondents noted between 2-4 issues for people depositing metadata in their repository (n=8 (17%) for 2 issues, n=12 (25%) for 3 issues, n=7 (15%) for 4 issues).

Figure 34 Critical Issues for Metadata Submitters (Repository Q8)

Critical issues for metadata submitters

% Respondents selecting the issue. Multiple answers encouraged

Write in comments [sic]:

- I'm only guessing at the above - we've not recently checked with researchers re. what the impediments are
- Lack of automation, lack of duplicate checking, lack of ability to harvest and update records on a large and automatic scale.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: REPOSITORY MANAGERS

- As the people entering the information are the maintainers/providers of these resources, they understand what metadata is and is for. As usual, time is always an issue and frustration when they have to edit some info manually (e.g. as our curators could not harvest it automatically)
- Translating from Producers metadata schema to ours (modified ISAD(G))
- Currently our researcher self-submit interface has a bug and doesn't always work.
- We have very low requirements but I have been in publishing systems that have been burdensome.
- Standard metadata fields not really a problem. Full text documentation about dataset creation much more problematic
- Lack of understanding of journal article version types and licensing

How do you interact with metadata

9. Where does your metadata go when it is exported to other systems? (select all that apply)

Figure 35 Metadata Destination When Exported (Repository Q9)

Metadata destination when exported

% respondents that selected location. Multiple answers encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

- We have a public API and an OAI-PMH interface, so we don't actually know all of the systems that consume our data. Also, search engines index it.
- Other aggregators i.e. ARIADNE, EUROPEANA, Etc...
- Partner institutions via direct API connection with our system. Not always libraries of those institutions -- sometimes research management offices. Funders also.
- Research Data Australia, DataCite when DOIs are minted for datasets
- Google Scholar, ROAR
- [no response]
- Aggregators like CORE, BASE, Trove
- Trove, OAIster, Search engines like Google Scholar, CORE
- digital library content hubs using OAI-PMH

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: REPOSITORY MANAGERS

- DPLA, Google Scholar
- Trove, OAlster, Google, Google Scholar
- DataONE
- linked data partners
- Google and other search indexes, or aggregators that use schema.org. As we mint DOIs obviously our metadata goes to DataCite. We use ORCID for the maintainers of the records but we do not (yet) send our metadata to them, but we plan to.
- Google Data Search, Mendeley Data
- GBIF
- Other Semantic Repositories like AgroPortal; Other Research Metadata Repositories like NCBI and LINCS
- Google
- we do no export
- None of the above, that I'm aware of. ETD metadata is also entered into the Library Catalog.
- internal RMS, external (government) research impact reporting, Google (OA objects only), National library catalogue (theses), university library catalogue (theses)

10. Which is true for the research objects that can be deposited in your repository? (select all that apply)

The chart below displays shortened names for the following choices:

- **Required metadata at deposit:** Repository-required metadata is presented at time of deposit
- **Deposit-ready by content owners:** Content can be made deposit-ready by owner or others easily
- **Deposit-ready in format/directory org:** Content is deposit-ready with respect to format(s) and/or directory organization
- **No duplicate content:** Content may not duplicate previously deposited research object
- **Other**

Figure 36 Characteristics of Deposited Research Objects (Repository Q10)

Characteristics of deposited research objects

% Respondents selecting the characteristic. Multiple answers encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

- We provide consulting to help donators clean-up their repo
- Exceptions are made depending on the value of the records.
- data agreement, assessment of appropriateness and priority
- metadata curated with ingest
- Sorry but this question is not clear to me. We have submission forms and therefore we guide the submitted to provide the metadata at that point; then it gets curated and harmonized in house and the maintainer can always update the record (that is checked by the in house curators at least once a year)
- I don't understand this question

11. Where are the critical issues in your workflows with respect to metadata required for inclusion in your repository? (select up to 5)

Average number of selections = 3

Figure 37 Source of Critical Metadata Issues in Workflow (Repository Q11)

Source of critical metadata issues in workflow

% Respondents selecting the issue. Multiple answers encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

- Critical issues re. ensuring quality of metadata, affiliation information is correct, re-use of metadata by the Research Office, etc.
- Inter-repositories/registries interoperability
- Applying the require controlled vocabulary (FoR)
- Full text documentation often lacking
- lack of universal standards; only basic metadata is generated atm
- Sorry, not real sure I understand the distinctions here. How do we define critical?

12. What are your methods to check the quality of the metadata in your system? (select all that apply)

Figure 38 Method to Check Metadata Quality (Repository Q12)

Method to check metadata quality

% Respondents selecting the choice. Multiple answers encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: REPOSITORY MANAGERS

- Working to build automated validation rules for ISBN, ISSN, DOI and ORCID
- All publications receive a HERDC classification. We've developed automated methods to identify C1 publications⁹ which have been taken up by certain faculties.
- Our internal curation is essential also for checking evolution and status of the resources registered (e.g., over time many standards and repositories are superseded by others or deprecated, or loose funds and are no longer maintained), and perform review of each record's description, communicating with the resource's maintainer as needed
- We are reliant on the Research Office to complete data quality checks, but these are not always done, resulting in significant double-handling of records.
- Automated checking other external systems
- Downloading information from repository and manually checking it

Metadata specifics

13. What pieces of information does your repository require for deposition? (select all that apply)

Figure 39 Required Metadata for Repository Deposition (Repository Q13)

Required metadata for repository deposition

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

⁹ Authors note: C1 publications is an Australian standard

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: REPOSITORY MANAGERS

Write in comments [sic]:

- Article ID, Commissioning body for reports, editors, place of publication, conference location, outlet for Creative Works, evidence of peer-review.
- curated at time of ingest
- FAST subject headings
- Field of Research and Socio-Economic Objects codes
- I have tried to answer this from the perspective of how these fields may map into software.
- instrument documentation (manuals, calibration sheets, etc)
- Peer review status
- publication status, peer review status, journal title (if a published article)
- Questions, mapping between ROs
- Re. copyright - this is generally held by the publisher, we don't expect researchers to provide a copyright statement.
- Some of these are only required for particular item types or scenarios
- Spatial location, temporal coverage period, contact, entity and attribute information, methods, sampling design, and much more
- We also have specific metadata for each of the record type we have (repositories/databases/knowledgebases, metadata/identifiers/reporting standards, data policies). We also have metadata that describes the interlinks between a e.g. repository and the metadata standard(s) the repository uses.
- We support creation of templates, so all the above could be included in a template.

14. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of metadata? (select all that apply)

Figure 40 Most Important Metadata Fields (Repository Q14)

Most important metadata fields

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

- Questions, mapping between ROs
- Globally unique identifier, ideally dereferenceable.
- Description information
- geographic extent, repository, domain controlled vocabularies
- persistent identifiers
- of course different context require different metadata - so what is the purpose here - preservation, dissemination?
- A unique, persistent ID, professional paper, benchmarks and/or tests
- methods, entity and attribute metadata
- The metadata capturing the relation(s) between and among the records (e.g. which database uses which metadata standards)
- Other contributors; geographic coverage
- Field of Research and Socio-Economic Objects codes

15. What metadata standard do you use for including objects in your repository? (select all that apply)

Figure 41 Metadata Standards Used for Objects in Your Repository (Repository Q15)

Metadata standards used for objects in your repository

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

Write in comments [sic]:

- DDI
- DDI-Lifecycle
- Qualified Dublin Core
- DataCite, EThOS uketd_dc
- Pure XML
- Combination of the above. Your list is rather library-centric. (I'm from earth science and biomedical communities.)
- ISO 19115
- modified ISAD(G)
- we have our own system but are able to map to other formats - it is a standard agnostic database - again different context require different metadata - these choices seem to focus on access and possibly content - but administrative and preservation metadata are needed too - premic among others
- We have our own internal schema.
- working towards codemeta
- EML, ISO 19115
- JSON LD (linked data) also annotated using schema.org vocabulary
- Local schema for some fields
- RDF will be generated for datasets when harvested by RDA
- own schema which is mapped to EML + DataCite XML

Researchers (n=49)

Tell us about you

2. What is your research field and/or topic?

The researchers reported specific fields of study or research, which were then more generally categorized:

Figure 42 Research Field and/or Topic (Researcher Q2)

Research field and/or topic

Summarized and grouped answers

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: RESEARCHERS

3. How long have you been working in this field?

The researcher group reported the ranges of years working in their respective fields.

Figure 43 Years in This Field (Researcher Q3)

Years in this field

% indicating the range

More than 30 years

5.6%

20-30 years

35.2%

5-10 years

27.8%

10-20 years

31.5%

4. Do you publish your research?

- 94% reported actively publishing their research

5. Do you collaborate with other researchers?

- 88% reported collaborating with other researchers. (2 respondents did not answer this question)

How do you interact with metadata

6. When you think of the term “metadata” what comes to mind? (free text responses summarized below)

When asked about their concept of metadata (when you think of the term “metadata” what comes to mind?), responses were generally categorized and distributed as in the figure below.

Figure 44 What Comes to Mind When You Hear the Term Metadata (Researcher Q6)

What comes to mind when you hear the term "metadata"?

Summarized and interpreted answers.

7. Does your research work include using research data management software?

Figure 45 Work Include Use of Research Data Management Software? (Researcher Q7)

Work include use of research data management software?

% responding

Metadata specifics

8. What do you consider to be the most important pieces of information about research objects in order to make them accessible and useful to others in your field in future? (select all that apply)

Figure 46 Most Important Metadata to Make Content Accessible & Useful (Researcher Q8)

Most important metadata to make content accessible & useful

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: RESEARCHERS

9. If you're trying to find a good research object (e.g., an article or dataset), what pieces of information are most helpful in finding what you seek? (select all that apply)

Figure 47 Most Important Metadata Fields When Finding Research Objects (Researcher Q9)

Most important metadata fields when finding research objects

% Respondents selecting the field. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

10. What are the top five pieces of information you look at to help you decide if you should read/download a paper or book chapter?

Figure 48 Important Metadata Fields When Choosing to Read a Resource (Researcher Q10)

Important metadata fields when choosing to read a resource

% including the field in their top five. Importance for those selecting: 5= most important; 1=least important

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: RESEARCHERS

11. If you're trying to decide whether or not to read an article or a book chapter when you see an interesting title or scan through a table of contents, what are the most important things for you to know about it before you read it in detail? (select all that apply)

Figure 49 Most Important Info When Deciding to Read an Article/Book Chapter (Researcher Q11)

Most important info when deciding to read an article/book chapter

% Respondents selecting the item. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

12. If you are trying to understand a data set, pieces of evidence or other scholarly artifacts you found or were sent to you by a colleague, what are the most critical things for you to know to evaluate credibility and usefulness before you can use it/them? (select all that apply)

Figure 50 Most Important Info When Evaluating Dataset/Evidence Credibility and Usefulness (Researcher Q12)

Most important info when evaluating dataset/evidence credibility and usefulness

% Respondents selecting the item. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

13. What traits usually prevent you from using a dataset or piece of evidence? (select all that apply)

Figure 51 Traits Preventing Dataset / Evidence Use (Researcher Q13)

Traits preventing dataset/evidence use

% Respondents selecting the item. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

14. Where do you store or deposit your data sets, pieces of evidence, or other scholarly artifacts after you have finished with them? (select all that apply)

Figure 52 Where datasets, Evidence, and Scholarly Artifacts are Stored (Researcher Q14)

Where datasets, evidence, and scholarly artifacts are stored

% Respondents selecting the item. (25% or more selecting the field) Multiple selections encouraged.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: RESEARCHERS

15. Which standardized metadata schema do you use to describe your research outputs when you publish them or post them online?

Figure 53 Metadata Standards Used When Publishing Your Research Outputs (Researcher Q15)

Metadata standards used when publishing your research outputs

% Respondents selecting the standard. Multiple selections encouraged.

Written in responses to “Other” for question 15:

- MathML
- ACM
- CERIF, bibtex
- I never heard about any
- DDI (entered by two respondents)
- Metadata schemas are automatically generated, so I just fill in forms
- ISO 19115, GCMD, SensorML, DDI
- CERIF and from there can generate most of the above
- FITS
- <https://github.com/lawdi/LAWD>

Cross-stakeholder Insights

Several questions were asked across stakeholder groups.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: CROSS-STAKEHOLDER INSIGHTS

A1. What metadata fields are most important? (Library Survey Q11; Publisher Survey Q11; Repository Manager Survey Q14; Researcher Survey Q8)

Table 8 Most Important Metadata Fields by Stakeholder Group

Most important metadata fields

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

	Librarian	Publisher	Repository	Researcher
Title	77%	93%	80%	90%
Author name(s)	70%	82%	80%	90%
Year and Date of publication	57%	89%	69%	86%
DOI	47%	89%	63%	72%
Abstract	25%	71%	43%	56%
Author ORCID(s)	23%	54%	45%	48%
Usage restrictions	32%	50%	51%	36%
Format of data (file types)	30%	32%	39%	28%
Volume (and Issue if relevant)	27%	46%	20%	34%
Author(s) affiliations	10%	50%	37%	30%
ISBN or other title identifier	27%	39%	31%	28%
ISSN	18%	43%	27%	30%
Record type	19%	32%	39%	20%
Researcher/Author generated keywords	24%	39%	20%	26%
Associated data sets	14%	29%	29%	26%
Page numbers	15%	39%	16%	24%
Grant ID(s)	8%	36%	37%	10%
Language of content	26%	21%	22%	20%
non-DOI article identifier	18%	18%	27%	26%
Funder Name(s)	9%	36%	22%	18%
Local controlled subject vocabulary	20%	25%	24%	10%
Funder ID(s)	6%	32%	24%	16%
Zotero				18%
Associated publications	9%	7%	29%	24%
Other - Write In	14%	14%	22%	18%
Size of content files	7%	14%	27%	14%
Mendeley				12%
LCSH Subjects	28%	11%	2%	6%
MeSH Subjects	14%	18%	2%	10%
Elocation ID	1%	18%	6%	12%
Endnote				8%
Refworks				2%
None of the above	1%	0%	0%	0%
Full text	0%	0%	0%	0%

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: CROSS-STAKEHOLDER INSIGHTS

A2. How many important fields were selected by survey type? (Library Survey Q11; Publisher Survey Q11; Repository Manager Survey Q14; Researcher Survey Q8)

On average, publishers selected more fields (11.4 on average) than the other stakeholders, and nearly 40% more fields than librarians who on average selected 6.8 of the fields listed. To accommodate fields that may not have been included, an “other” option with write-in text was provided. Table 2 summarizes these responses for each group.

Table 9 Number of Important Metadata Fields

Number of important metadata fields

Average number of selected fields by stakeholder group.

Stakeholder	Avg # fields selected	% selecting “other” / Avg # items written in	Avg # selected fields (accounting for write-in)
Librarians	6.6	14% / 1 item ¹⁰	6.8
Publishers	11.1	14% / 2 items	11.4
Repository Managers	9.1	22% / 2 items ¹¹	9.6
Researchers	9.5	18% / 1 item	9.7

¹⁰ Several librarians pointed out that the field importance depends on the research field.

¹¹ Several repository managers indicated that field importance depends on the purpose - preservation/ dissemination

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: CROSS-STAKEHOLDER INSIGHTS

A3. Fields more likely to be selected by Publishers than other stakeholder groups (Library Survey Q11; Publisher Survey Q11; Repository Manager Survey Q14; Researcher Survey Q8)

Table 10 Metadata Fields Significantly More Important to Publishers

Metadata fields significantly more important to publishers

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged. > 20% difference is highlighted

Field	Publishers	Librarians		Repository		Researchers	
	%	%	Difference from Publishers	%	Difference from Publishers	%	Difference from Publishers
Yr. & date of pub	89%	57%	-32%	69%	-20%	86%	-3%
DOI	89%	47%	-43%	63%	-26%	72%	-17%
Abstract	71%	25%	-46%	43%	-29%	56%	-15%
Author(s) ORCID	54%	23%	-31%	45%	-9%	48%	-6%
Volume / issue	46%	27%	-19%	20%	-26%	34%	-12%
Author(s) affiliation	50%	10%	-40%	37%	-13%	30%	-20%
ISSN	43%	18%	-25%	27%	-16%	30%	-13%
Page numbers	39%	15%	-25%	16%	-23%	24%	-15%
Grant ID(s)	36%	8%	-28%	37%	1%	10%	-26%
Funder Name(s)	36%	9%	-27%	22%	-13%	18%	-18%
Funder ID(s)	32%	6%	-26%	24%	-13%	16%	-18%

Figure 54 Metadata Fields Significantly More Important to Publishers

Metadata fields significantly more important to publishers

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

Metadata Survey Results Summary

Stakeholder: CROSS-STAKEHOLDER INSIGHTS

A4. Fields more likely to be selected by Librarians than other stakeholder groups (Library Survey Q11; Publisher Survey Q11; Repository Manager Survey Q14; Researcher Survey Q8)

Table 11 Metadata Fields Significantly Different in Importance to Librarians

Metadata fields significantly different in importance to librarians

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged. > 20% difference is highlighted: Red = librarians were less likely to indicate that the field was important; Blue = librarians were more likely to.

Field	Librarians	Publishers		Repository		Researchers	
	%	%	Difference from Librarians	%	Difference from Librarians	%	Difference from Librarians
Yr. & date of pub	57%	89%	32%	69%	13%	86%	29%
DOI	47%	89%	43%	63%	17%	72%	25%
Abstract	25%	71%	46%	43%	18%	56%	31%
Author(s) ORCID	23%	54%	31%	45%	22%	48%	25%
Volume / issue	27%	46%	19%	20%	-7%	34%	7%
Author(s) affiliation	10%	50%	40%	37%	27%	30%	20%
Grant ID(s)	8%	36%	28%	37%	29%	10%	2%
Language of content	26%	21%	-5%	22%	-4%	20%	-6%
Local controlled subject vocab	20%	25%	5%	24%	4%	10%	-10%
LCSH subjects	28%	11%	-18%	2%	-26%	6%	-22%
MeSH Subjects	14%	18%	4%	2%	-12%	10%	-4%

Metadata fields significantly different in importance to librarians

% Respondents selecting the field. Multiple selections encouraged.

